

UBURU WOMEN AND THE SALT LAKE: A HISTORICAL PERSPECTIVE FROM EARLIEST TIME TO 2020

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Abstract: *This paper examined Uburu women and the salt lake, from the earliest time to 2020. Uburu community in Ohaozara LGA of Ebonyi State is one of the few fortunate and privileged communities blessed with salt lake. This salt lake which exhibits the wonders of nature is a thing of beauty, great joy and blessing, not only to the indigenes of Uburu community but also Ebonyi State in particular and Nigeria in general. The production of salt from this lake is solely done by women even till today. This is largely due to the fact that the activities of salt production such as fetching water and firewood, cooking etc are feminine activities, thus, the men folks concentrate on farming and hunting, leaving the job of salt making to the women. The researcher used the primary and secondary sources to generate the required data mainly from oral interview, intelligence reports, books, journals, articles among others. The researcher also adopted the multidisciplinary approach to further enrich the available historical data. The major findings of the study revealed that Uburu women dominated the salt industry; salt production in Uburu is purely women's affair, through a technology that was indigenously improvised by Uburu women. They improvised a means of processing the salt water by passing it through the fire and the end product is iodized salt. The study further revealed that in pre-colonial and colonial Uburu society, salt was one of the main stay of Uburu economy. It attracted traders from all works of life to Uburu market called Nkwuroto. Women also travelled round neighbouring communities on foot in search of better bargains for their product. In the beginning, women in their menstrual period were not allowed to enter the lake. To ensure compliance, women were made to enter the lake in their nude only. The advent of civilization led to the abolishing of that practice through a crusade championed by 'Ojimba' Age Grade led by Osuji Njoku Obasi*

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(Una) and Osuji Obasi Ukpa (Agodi) in 1948. The paper recommended that a modern salt industry should be established in Uburu community. Government should mechanize the salt lake to meet global needs. The paper concluded that the salt lake attracted tourists from within and outside Nigeria which produced considerable revenue to the community. Researchers as well visited the local technology sites (Onu Ebe) from research centers and institutions of learning.

Introduction

Salt is universally recognized as an indispensable substance. This is certain because of its innumerable importance in the daily activities of man. The use of salt in our homes, chemical industries and pharmaceutical industries are some of the importance attached to salt. Even in the historical times, salt helped in many ways in the sustenance of man on planet earth. A good example is one recorded in the Bible where Elisha the prophet used salt to heal the bad waters and the unproductive lands of Jericho.

Ude (2018) opined that salt is a mineral composed primarily of sodium chloride (Naci) a chemical compound belonging to the larger class of salts. In view of these facts, it is undoubtedly clear that the presence of a source of salt is of a great wealth to any community where it is located. Uburu community is one of those few communities blessed with salt lake. Uburu women dominated the activities of the salt lake.

Conceptual Clarification

Salt is a mineral composed primarily of sodium chloride (Naci), a chemical compound belonging to the larger class of salts (Ude, 2018). Salt is present in vast quantities in sea-water, where it is the main mineral constituent. Salt is one of the oldest and most ubiquitous food seasonings, and salting is an important method of food preservation. Salt is essential for human life, and saltiness is one of the basic human tastes. Salt became an important article of trade and was transported by boat across the Mediterranean Sea, along specially built salt roads and across the Sahara in camel caravans (Okpara, 2006).

Ude (2018) posits that some of the earliest evidence of salt processing dates to around 8000 years ago, when people living in an area in what is now known as the country of Romania were boiling spring water to extract the salts, a salt work in China dates to approximately to the same period. To Okike (2023) salt is processed from salt mines/lakes, and by the evaporation of sea water (sea salt) or

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mineral-rich spring water in shallow pools. Okike (2023) further opined that of the annual global production of around two hundred million tones of salt, only about 6% is used for human consumption. Other uses include water conditioning processes and agricultural uses.

Origin of Uburu Salt Lake

Uburu salt lake is situated in the heart of Uburu town. It is located between three villages namely Amenu, Umuchima and Urobo, these villages have road tracks leading directly to the salt lake (Uneke, 1992). To Offia (2023), Uburu salt lake was discovered by one Oke- a hunter from Awgu Local Government Area of Enugu State. In the events that culminated in the brine discovery. It happened that in one of Oke's hunting expeditions he became thirsty and needed water to quench his thirst, in search for water to quench his thirst with his dog, Oke saw his hunting dog with wet legs suggesting the presence of water. Offia (2023) further narrated that Oke became anxious to find the water since it was dry season. He therefore followed his dog a little distance and saw an area covered with what he thought was water. However, on tasting the liquid, Oke frowned at insipid taste, only to discover that the water before him was salt water.

Chukwu (1986) subscribed to the above narration by asserting that Oke took conical tablets of salt to Agwu Agbor to show his wife-

Ogodo. And in another hunting expedition, Oke showed his hunting colleague Chima the salt water he discovered and as it were, Chima became an associate in the salt lake discovery. To harness the salt lake effectively, Oke left Agwu- Agbor with his family and established a permanent home in the present Uburu community. Hamilton (1938) lent credence to above facts when he wrote; "The fourteen villages which make up Uburu Community migrated into this new land of salt from different communities in Igbo land".

Ogwu village was the first village to settle in Uburu community through their progenitor and founder, Oke, who with his wife started to populate the area before other people who made up other villages started to migrate into the area when they heard of the salt lake, and its economic worth (Akpa 2023). In this sense, it could be argued that the salt lake predates the origin and settlement of people in Uburu. Afigbo (1981) asserts that the salt trade in Uburu was ancient indeed, at least predating the fifteenth century.

Salt Production Period in Uburu

Ibrahim (1997) asserts that almost all local industries in Nigeria with the exception of iron works are domains of women. The Uburu salt industry has been dominated by the female folk. Salt production in Uburu is relatively a non-seasonal enterprise. As Offia (2023) states that

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during the favourable periods (months of October through March) the production output of Uburu salt tends to be at its peak. To account for this is the fact that there are little or no rains within these months and the salinity of the brine remains high. Because of the high concentration of the salt water, production becomes quicker and easier.

During this period, the women who engage in salt production often do not have to undergo the various procedures of filtering, boiling and evaporation repeatedly. They just fetch the concentrated salt water, boil and evaporate the little water content leaving ready salt for sale or immediate domestic use.

However, during the rainy season which stretches from the months of April through September, the salt lake is over flooded by the Esu River, which usually over flow its banks during this season. The over flooding reduces in a comparatively great extent the salinity of the salt lake.

Una (2023) posits that what the women salt producers do at this period of over flooding and lower concentration is to fetch the salt water, pour it into the filtering pot 'Ite Ochichi' which is already containing dried up muddy salt from the 'Onu Ebe'. Having poured the less containing salt water, producers would then wash out the already stored highly concentrated salt inside the 'Ite Ochichi.' It is then filtered

into the 'Nja – Ugbani' placed below and later boiled and evaporated for real salt.

The Salt Production Process in Uburu

Ude (2018) asserts that salt production in Uburu is purely women's affair through a technology that was indigenously produced by women. The process involves much labour, women intending to join the business of salt making was usually initiated by Ogwu women. To begin the local salt production process, women acquired a space of land each, at the bank of the lake and position three or five pots depending on her ability. To Ogonna (2003) these pots are called 'ofufu,' another bigger pot called 'Onini' would be placed beside the pots with those items in place; a woman has constructed her local salt factory known as 'onuebe.' The pots on tripod would allow for small opening while a clay conical device would be placed underneath each pot. The conical dish is called 'Nja Agbani'.

According to Ogo (2023) to commence the production process they use a flat metal object called 'Atakpa' to collect 'earth' from the water-bed of the lake. The collected earth would be used to fill the pots sitting on the tripod, the (ofufu) to cover the 'earth'. The small holes at their bottom would be blocked to avoid leakages, while the pots would remain with the content overnight. In the morning, the blocked holes in the pots are opened; it is called 'irufu

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eja'. This would give way for the filtrate to be dropping into the clay conical dish 'Nja Agbani' beneath. Later in the day, the filtrate in the 'Nja Agba' is collected and taken home for boiling. It is called 'Ochichi'.

The big pot, 'Onini' beside the pots on the tripod 'ofufu' is used to preserve the salt water fetched from the lake to be poured in the other pots when filled with 'earth' or to retain the filtrate water 'Ochichi' before gradually being taken home for boiling. The filtrate (concentrated saline) water brought home 'Ochichi' is poured in a drum sitting on a tripod with enough fire in place. It consumes enough fire-woods as such adequate provisions are made for firewood before the boiling commences.

Ude (2018) explained that the boiling does not stay until crystals of salt are produced. At the course of the boiling, salt would start to form in the drum. The salt maker gradually collects it and puts into a small conical clay dish called 'Nja Agba'. The salt in small dish 'Nja Agba' is passed through a baking process under other smaller tripod on fire too. It is at this point that the salt is baked into different portable sizes that featured in the popular Uburu market.

The Uburu Salt Lake and its Taboos

Taboos are parts of ingredients which make up the culture of a people. In one sentence, culture connotes the sum total of a peoples' way of life.

Taboos are one of the measuring instruments of culture (Okpara, 2006).

There are some rituals and customs associated with the Uburu salt lake and to contravene them was an abomination. The contravention of such forbidden aspects of the salt lake called for an immediate purificatory sacrifice under the auspices of the Chief Priest to placate the wrath of 'Anya Mmahi' against the particular offender. Uchenna (2023) deposited that one of the vital customs associated with the salt lake in Uburu was the women initiation into the guild of salt producers. Another was the approach of women to the salt lake during their monthly cycle which was a forbidden act. Initially, men were not to be seen around the salt lake, but the dynamics of culture have violated this taboo, women now go to the salt lake not naked but well dressed.

Nnenna (2023) asserts, 'to appease the gods of 'Anya Mmahi' and to keep the salinity of the lake, annual sacrifices were made to the salt lake. For instance, on one occasion, it was believed that the 'Anya Mmahi' was not happy with the people and so for fear of the lake drying up, the priest of Mmahi who was consulted by the women told them that a person was needed as a sacrifice to appease 'Anya Mmahi's' wrath. In fact, this practice of human sacrifice to appease the god of the brine (Anya Mmahi) continued up to the end of the last century. Nevertheless, slaves were usually the victims of

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this sacrifice. Isichi (1970) confirmed this assertion by noting that slaves from Ohuhu called 'Ovulabo' were carried to Uburu where they were sacrificed to the spirit of the brine. Arguably, taboos acted as a remote control in the activities of women in the salt industry.

Marketing of the Salt

Markets are the oil that lubricates the wheel of trade and industry. Without a market, the producer will continue to produce at the subsistence degree, which enhances his or her survival, if at all, at the minimal level. Writing on the importance of trade and market, Afigbo (1981) emphasized that although subsidiary to agriculture, trade was nonetheless an important aspect of Igbo economic activity. Just as "Chukwu" (God) is believed to have institutionalized trade and marketing by creating the Igbo market days naming them after four heavenly fish mongers, each whom went round Igbo land establishing markets bearing his name.

Salt was a scarce commodity in pre-colonial times, it was considered an important item of trade. The famous Uburu market fondly called 'Nkwuroto' meaning standing, so called because there were no seats and stalls, therefore marketers displayed and sold their goods standing, acted as a base for the Uburu salt trade. As a spring board, this market was the place from where salt trade was carried to other

places and provided a good platform for cultural exchanges between Uburu and her visitors from far and near communities. Echoing the above assertion, Hamilton (1939) opined that 'Not only do people from all the surrounding clans within striking distance flock to Uburu market, but also regular traders travelled by lorries from such distant places such as Enugu, Aba and Onitsha.

Among the goods that formed the bulk of the trade were farm products and livestock like horses, goats, cloths, gunpowder, iron products and many other goods which were exchanged with Uburu salt. From the northern Igbo land came the Nsukka, Awka and Agbaja traders, from the south, came the Aro through Bende and Uzuakoli via Okposi to Uburu. Uburu market therefore became a trading terminus for both the northern and southern Igbo traders and even to beyond.

Hodder and Ukwu (1969) realized this fact when they opined that the Aro established trade fair in Uburu through which they maximized the salt and slave trade. Isichi (1970) also points out that it was for the procurement of salt and slaves in Uburu big market that the influence of the Aro presence became well pronounced in Uburu. The Aros who were renowned traders rivaled with several other traders because of their major control of the trading transactions. No wonder Afigbo (1981) recorded the

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experience of Nsukka traders by portraying the fact that, 'The Aku on their side even set up a system which sought to side-track the Aro system through establishing direct access to Uburu for salt and to Bende for imported European goods. For purpose of effective commercial enterprises trading transactions carried out on the 'Nkwuroto' were in the interval of six to eight market days. Traders to the Uburu market usually arrived Uburu ahead of the actual market day.

Problems and Prospects of the Salt Industry

Problems associated with indigenous industries in Nigeria varies from one industry to another, the Uburu salt product, like other indigenous manufacturers, suffer from price fluctuation and competition from imported salt. Another problem of the industry is that the producers incur losses through the breaking of their pots (Nja, Oku or Eju) used for storing and boiling the salt brine. As a result, women and their salt trading husbands resorted to frequent replacement of the 'Oku- and Nja' such replacement amount to waste.

The next major problem confronting the salt industry is lack of patronage by the government. The apparent lack of interest and indifference on the part of the government led to several unfulfilled promises on the mechanization of the salt lake.

It is important to state that measures could be taken to alleviate the problems being encountered in the management of indigenous industries. Uburu people and particularly the womenfolk need to be enlightened on the obvious benefits they could derive through the mechanization of the salt industry. Also, Ebonyi state government should hasten up and take over the salt lake for mechanization. The government should establish salt and allied chemical industries which will produce the much needed salt and other raw materials for the industrial take off of the state and create job opportunities for the teeming population of unemployed school leavers.

Impact of the Salt Lake to Uburu Community

The presence of the salt lake in Uburu has created an impact on the roles and status of Uburu women vis-à-vis their contribution to the community. It has brought a lot of changes and development to the women and their households. Due to wealth from the salt boom between 1967- 1973, women acquired titles like 'Orimmeji' (title for a woman who killed a horse) 'Osunankata (This title was equivalent to Ezeji- King of Yam), 'Ogoo Nwa Uji' (This title places the woman on equal footing with men). Indeed, due to commercial enterprise with other towns, and communities, Uburu people learnt social norms from them, and inter

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marriages took place. The salt lake attracted tourists from within and outside Nigeria which produced considerable revenue to the community. Researchers as well visited the local technology sites (Onu ebe) from institutions of higher learning and research centres (Ude, 2008)

Conclusion

This study is a bold attempt to examine the role of women in the development of Uburu salt industry. Evidence from the study tends to show that women dominated Uburu salt industry. The salt lake and 'Nkwuroto' market attracted people from far and near for trade and commerce which impacted positively on the economic history of Uburu community.

Furthermore, the study has demonstrated to a great extent that Uburu salt lake attracted tourists and researchers from within and outside Nigeria which produced considerable

revenue to the community. The study also revealed that the salt industry suffers lack of patronage by the government, price fluctuation and competition from imported salt. The salt industry impacted positively on the status of Uburu women and has been an edifice for revenue generation in Uburu. Finally, the study recommended that a modern salt industry should be established in Uburu community. Government should mechanize the salt lake to meet global demands.

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Nnenna Uzor	61	F	Salt Maker	Uburu	August 6, 2023
Regina Akpa	83	F	Retired Teacher	Uburu	April 28, 2023
Rose Akpa	53	F	Salt Maker	Uburu	August 25, 2023
Ogo Chukwu	71	F	Former Salt Maker	Uburu	April 20, 2023
Ogonna Igwe	73	F	Former Salt Maker	Uburu	April 11, 2023
Ngene Onu	43	M	Teacher	Uburu	June 13, 2023
Okike Emmanuel	37	M	Civil Servant	Uburu	April 16, 2023
Onu Nickolas	38	M	Business Man	Uburu	May 15, 2023

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